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Impact Factor: 2.48

Cite this paper as : Avani Bisht, Sachin Panwar, Shubham Chauhan, Vipin Rawat, Sarim Khan, Sagar Pokhrel, Keerat Singh (2017). STUDY OF PERFORMANCE OF GEOGRID AND SOIL INTERFACE USING VERTICAL PULLOUT TEST, *International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research, Volume 4,(Issue 2, Feb-Apr-2017), pp 49-54 . ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print),*

STUDY OF PERFORMANCE OF GEOGRID AND SOIL INTERFACE USING VERTICAL PULLOUT TEST

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Abstract:

The use of geosynthetics is to improve the performance of foundations when constructing on soft compressible foundation soils. The material properties of geosynthetics are important to their use in various applications. Geosynthetics have become well established construction materials for geotechnical and environmental applications in most parts of the world. This report presents a vertical pullout test (VPT) developed to measure the peak interface friction angle and cohesion between soil and planar geosynthetic products. Two types of geo-synthetic material of different sizes (150mm by 150mm and 300mm by 300mm) were evaluated using the pullout test. Series of pull-out tests were performed to study the interface characteristics between geogrids and soils. Two geogrids were used to investigate the interaction properties with clay. The function of geogrid reinforcement and the geogrid-soil interaction mechanism were mainly studied by experimental methods.

KEYWORDS - geo-synthetic material, cohesive soil, vertical pull-out test, triaxial shear test.

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil reinforcement plays a key role in the construction of earth structures as it works as an alternative for the embankments and retaining wall projects. There is a huge demand of it in today's

construction work due to many factors which incorporates low cost, simple construction techniques, reliability and its adaptability to different site conditions. By providing geosynthetic as reinforcement material in the soil, the performance of soil in tension is enhanced by the tension carrying capacity of geosynthetics. It improves the engineering behaviour of the soil mass and improves the bearing capacity of soft soil, enhances stability of steep slopes and reduces earth pressure behind retaining structures. Reinforcement mechanism is influenced by properties of interface between the reinforcement and the geologic media. And these interface properties between the geosynthetic material and the surrounding media can be investigated by conducting pullout test in the laboratory.

Many researchers have worked over it and have developed numerous techniques to measure the interface properties of geosynthetics. This paper is about vertical pullout test (VPT), in which the geosynthetic material is embedded vertically in the soil sample and is tested for evaluating the interface properties of it with the cohesive soil. The test consists of pulling the vertically fixed geogrid out from the soil. The shear resistance of the soil and grid differs from the soil alone. The grid opening permits the different sized soil particles to interlock and generate a mechanical bond between the surrounding soil layer and the grid. Consequently, vertical movement of the soil is immediately resisted by the grid which in effect, is reinforcing the surrounding cohesive soil. Two types of

biaxial woven and non-woven geosynthetic materials of different sizes have been used in this experiment. The internal angle of friction ϕ was determined using the triaxial shear test. The results from the Triaxial Shear Test and the Vertical Pullout Test were compared.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This paper is about the test and with the help of this test; the method to measure the interface shear stresses and shear strength parameters for soil and geosynthetic is developed. To measure the internal friction angle of the cohesive soil which is further needed in the main test of VPT, triaxial shear test is to be performed.

A. Triaxial shear test

A triaxial shear test is a method carried out in a cell to measure the mechanical properties of soils (e.g., sand, clay), rock and other granular materials or powders. This method determines the compressive strength of cylindrical specimens of cohesive soils in an undisturbed condition, using a strain controlled application of the axial compression-test load where the specimen is subjected to a confining fluid pressure in a triaxial chamber.

The method provides for the measurement of the total stresses applied to the specimen and provides data for determining strength properties and stress-strain relations for soils. The solid specimen, cylindrical in shape, is subjected to direct stresses acting in three mutually perpendicular directions. σ_1 , major principle stress which is applied in vertical direction, σ_2 and σ_3 (intermediate minor principle stress) applied in horizontal direction in the form of fluid pressure.

It consists of two stages. In first stage, a soil sample is set in the tri-axial cell and confining pressure is then applied. In second stage, additional axial stress or deviator stress is applied which induces the shear stresses in the sample.

Fig 1: Specimen of Triaxial Shear Test

The cylindrical specimen as shown in Fig. 1 is encased in a rubber membrane and sealed at the bottom as well as the loading cap at the top by rubber O-rings.

The membrane is used to prevent the pressurized cell fluid, which is usually water, from penetrating into the soil specimen. The triaxial cell is filled with water at the required pressure, thus subjecting the soil specimen to all around pressure. This is called the cell pressure of the confining pressure that is σ_3 .

The vertical stress is applied through proving ring which is equal to $(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)$ so that the total stress on the top of the specimen is equal to $(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 + \sigma_3) = \sigma_d + \sigma_3$. $(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)$ is known as deviator stress. It is desirable to maintain the self pressure with the help of Skempton & Bishop Apparatus.

B. Vertical Pullout Test

The VPT consists of pulling out a vertically embedded geosynthetic from the soil and measuring the maximum force or load required to mobilize the geosynthetic-soil interface. In VPT, the lateral earth pressure applied by the soil on the two faces of a piece of geosynthetic placed vertically in between the soil layers is utilized as the normal stress.

To achieve greater normal stresses, surcharge load is placed on both sides of the geosynthetic. The shearing force is applied by vertically pulling out the geosynthetic to mobilize it. The peak value of the vertical pullout shearing force is recorded. It is tested in two different geogrid of different material that are Polypropylene BX Geogrid and Poliester BX Geogrid.

C. Testing Procedure

A sample of the geogrid is cut to the desired dimensions. Test was performed on two geogrids of different sizes: 150 mm by 150 mm, and 300 mm by 300 mm. The geogrids used were Polypropylene BX Geogrid and Poliester BX Geogrid.

The sample needs to have at least additional 5cm height in the loading direction to allow mounting using the clamps and to allow clearance above the soil.

The sample is placed in the clamp and held vertically inside the container. Soil is placed around the sides while maintaining a vertical alignment of the geogrid. The soil sample is placed in three layers until the desired embedded length is achieved.

The soil can be compacted with a rammer by applying 25 blows on each layer to achieve a target unit weight. Surcharge load was added using bricks to

achieve the desired normal stress. The machine is operated to pull the geogrid completely vertically out.

(a)

(b)

Fig 2: (a) Geogrid clamped for VPT,
(b) Geogrid embedded vertically in the soil for testing

(a)

(b)

Fig 3: (a) VPT setup, (b) Surcharge load is added using bricks

D. Analysis

The lateral earth pressure and the lateral surcharge pressure are summed up to determine the normal stresses acting on the geogrid during the vertical pullout test. The normal stresses on the geogrid (horizontal) due to the soil and surface surcharge load are determined at a given point and the average normal stress over a finite area is calculated.

$$\text{Average normal stress } (\sigma_i)_{\text{avg}} = \frac{(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3 + \sigma_4)}{4} \tag{1}$$

Where:

$\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ and σ_4 are normal stresses at location i on the embedded portion of the geogrid.

$(\sigma_i)_{\text{avg}}$ = average of the stresses at the location.

The normal force over the incremental area is determined and the values are integrated over the embedded area of one side of the geogrid to determine the total normal force.

Total normal force:

$$N = \sum (\sigma_i)_{\text{avg}} \times (dH \times dB) \tag{2}$$

Where:

dH and dB = length and width of the grid block used to estimate the stresses on the geogrid.

The normal stress is determined using the above discussed equation. The shear stress is calculated, as shown in equation 4, by dividing the peak vertical pullout force by the embedded area of the geogrid.

These calculations are performed in a spreadsheet program.

$$(3) \quad \text{Normal stress: } \sigma = \frac{N}{B \times H}$$

$$(4) \quad \text{Shear Stress: } \tau = \frac{F_{vpp}}{2 \times B \times H_c}$$

Where:

F_{vpp} = peak vertical pullout force,

B = width of the geogrid, and

H_c = embedded height (or length) of the geogrid.

To compute the value of the interface friction angle and cohesion, the graph is being plotted between the various values of normal stresses and shear stresses calculated from the above equations (3) and (4).

III. MATERIALS

A. Soil

The fine-grained soil was used in this study. The liquid limit of the soil was 28.52 % and its plastic limit was 19.79%. The plasticity index came out to be 8.21% which means the soil has low plasticity. The value of permeability of soil came out to be 5.0648×10^{-4} . The optimum moisture content of the soil was 10%.

B. Geogrids

Two types of geogrids were used; Fig. 4 below shows the photographs of the geogrids used in the following test. The geogrid specimens used in the study were 1.5 mm thick. The sizes of the geogrids that were tested: 150 mm by 150 mm, and 300 mm by 300 mm. These dimensions refer to the embedded area.

Fig 4: Polypropylene BX Geogrid and Polyester BX Geogrid

IV. Results

A. Triaxial Shear Test

The Triaxial Shear Test was used to determine the internal friction angle of the soils used in this study. Tables below shows the results obtained from the triaxial shear test for clayey soil. The values obtained from the test were:

TABLE I: VALUES OF DIFFERENT PARAMETERS OF STRESSES

Cell pressure (KN/m ²)	100	200
Deviator stress at failure (KN/m ²)	300	410
Pore water pressure at failure (KN/m ²)	-45	-15

TABLE II: OBSERVATION TABLE OF VALUES OF MAJOR AND MINOR PRINCIPLE STRESSES

Test number	σ_y	$(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)_f$	σ_{1f}	u_f	σ'_{3f}	σ'_{1f}
1.	100	300	400	-45	145	445
2.	200	410	610	-15	215	625

TABLE III

EVALUATION TABLE OF MOHR-COULOMB CIRCLE

Serial number	Principle stresses		Distance from origin	Radius of circle
	σ_1	σ_2		
1.	400	100	250m	150m
2.	610	200	405m	205m
3.	445	145	295m	150m
4.	625	215	420m	205m

The values of $C = 50 \text{ KN/m}^2$ and $\phi = 15^\circ$ for one set of normal and shear stresses, and

The value of $C' = 30 \text{ KN/m}^2$ and $\phi' = 25^\circ$ for another set of normal and shear stresses.

B. Vertical Pullout Test

The first step in the evaluation of the VPT was to determine the geogrid size that would give representative and consistent interface strength parameters. Hence, two sizes (150 mm by 150 mm, and 300 mm by 300 mm) of geogrid were tested with clay

TABLE IV: OBSERVATION READINGS OF VERTICAL PULLOUT FORCES ACTING ON DIFFERENT GEOGRIDS USED

Serial Number	Geogrids Used	Reading of Load	Normal Stresses on 15cm size Polyester BX Geogrid	Shear Stresses on 15cm size Polypropylene BX Geogrid	Normal Stresses on 30cm size Polyester BX Geogrid	Shear Stresses on 30cm size Polypropylene BX Geogrid
1.	Poliester Geogrid	16 KN	1.038 KN/m ²	355.55KN/m ²	0.259 KN/m ²	88.89 KN/m ²
2.	P.P. Geogrid	24 KN	1.038 KN/m ²	533.33KN/m ²	0.259 KN/m ²	133.33 KN/m ²

Fig 5: VPT results for clay

The graph in Fig. 5 shows that the normal stresses applied to the geogrid during the VPTs were lower in magnitude than the stresses applied during the Triaxial Shear Test.

Hence, the interface properties measured are more appropriate where the vertical stress levels are relatively small or where preliminary values are adequate.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Soil-grid interaction is very significant for reinforced soil behaviour as it improves soil properties and positively influences inter-particle stresses and lowers permanent deformation of structures.

Geosynthetics have great potential to be used as cost-effective solutions for several engineering problems. This paper explained the method to evaluate the values of interface friction parameters which are playing a significant role in the interface mechanism.

A vertical pullout test (VPT) was developed to estimate the interface friction parameters for the interface between geogrid and fine-grained soils at relatively low normal stresses. The test apparatus uses inexpensive components. The method was easy.

In general, the coefficient of interaction decreases with increase in geosynthetic depth. The maximum average shear stress occurs at the top of the specimen and decreases gradually along the depth of the geosynthetic specimen. Both the biaxial geogrid used in this test exhibit strain hardening. The compaction density of clay will not only influence pull-out interface strength, but also affect the development of pull-out curves.

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